

Mothers and Fathers: Do They Differ in the Advice They Give Their Children About Bullying?

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Parents play a significant role in children's bullying involvement. As a way of engaging in bullying prevention, parents can choose certain strategies and give their children advice on how to address a situation as a bullying perpetrator or a victim. However, consistent knowledge about parents' preferred strategies when talking about bullying involvement is lacking. Moreover, little is known whether mothers and fathers differ in the kind of advice about bullying involvement they give to their children. This study aims to fill these gaps by examining what kind of advice parents give to their children regarding their involvement in bullying and whether mothers and fathers choose different approaches. We used data from the CHALLENGE project (N=3,798), which targeted parents of children attending Finnish primary schools. Parents were asked how likely they were to choose 19 specific strategies if their child was involved in bullying as a victim or a perpetrator. In the case of victimisation, parents prefer to advise their child to tell their teacher (M=4.80, SD=0.55) or promise their child they would think together about a solution (M=4.81, SD =0.50). Regarding bullying, parents prefer to say that their child needs to stop bullying immediately (M=4.92, SD=0.39) or try to explain that bullying can hurt (M=4.89, SD=0.43). Linear regression models showed that mothers scored higher in the majority of items. In contrast, fathers are more likely to choose not to say much, because bullying for both victims and bullies is a part of growing up, and advise their children to ignore bullies or to get back at them. Findings can help develop effective strategies that take into account differences between mothers and fathers.